

Thermodynamic, ultrasonic and refractive index measurement of hydrazones in dimethylformamide at different temperatures

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Abstract : Density (ρ), speed of sound (u), viscosity (η) and refractive index (n_D) of 2-hydroxy-5-chloroisonicotinoylhydrazone (HCAIH) and 2-hydroxy-5-methylisonicotinoylhydrazone (HMAIH) have been measured in *N,N*-dimethylformamide at temperatures 298.15, 303.15, 308.15 and 313.15 K. These measurements have been performed to evaluate some important thermodynamic, and acoustic parameters. The apparent molar volume (V_ϕ) and apparent molar compressibility (K_ϕ) of hydrazones in DMF were also calculated. Partial molar volume (V_ϕ^0) and partial molar compressibility (K_ϕ^0) were estimated by using the values of (V_ϕ) and (K_ϕ), at infinite dilution. The viscosity data have been analyzed using the Jones-Dole equation, and the viscosity *B*-coefficients are calculated. Refractive index data were used to calculate molar refractivity of solutions. The results have been discussed in the light of various types of interactions occurring in solution.

Keywords : Hydrazones, speed of sound, solvation number, partial molar volume, molar refraction, molecular interactions.

Introduction

Hydrazones are novel compounds with anticonvulsant, antidepressant, analgesic, anti-inflammatory, antiplatelet, antimalarial, antimicrobial, antimycobacterial, antitumoral, vasodilator, antiviral and antischistosomiasis activities^{1,2}. Hydrazones possessing an azomethine -NHN=CH- proton constitute an important class of compounds for new drug development. Therefore, many researchers have synthesized these compounds as target molecule and evaluated their biological activities. The knowledge of physicochemical behavior of drug plays important role in understanding their physiological action which highly dependent on the solution behavior³⁻⁶. These observations have been guiding for the development of new hydrazones that possess varied biological activities.

N,N-Dimethylformamide, as a polar solvent, is certainly to some extent associated by dipole-dipole interactions, and is of particular interest because of the absence of any significant structural effect due to lack of hydrogen bond, therefore, it may work as an aprotic, protophilic solvent with large dipole moment and high dielectric constant ($\mu = 3.24$ D and $\epsilon = 36.71$)⁷.

In the present paper we reports the densities (ρ), speed

of sound (u), viscosity (η) and refractive indices (n_D) of 2-hydroxy-5-chloroisonicotinoylhydrazone (HCAIH) and 2-hydroxy-5-methylisonicotinoylhydrazone (HMAIH) in dimethylformamide at temperatures 298.15, 303.15, 308.15 and 313.15 K. Various acoustic and thermodynamic parameters viz. adiabatic compressibility (β_s), intermolecular free length (L_f), specific impedance (Z), relaxation strength (r), relative association (R_A), internal pressure (P), solvation number (S_n) etc. including apparent molar volume (V_ϕ) and apparent molar compressibility (K_ϕ) have been computed. Refractive index data were used to calculate molar refractivity (R_D) of solutions. All these parameters are discussed in term of solute-solvent and solute-solute interactions occurring in solution.

Experimental

Isonicotinoylhydrazones were synthesized by known method by condensation reaction of hydroxy acetophenones and isonicotinic hydrazide in our laboratory and recrystallized and used. The purity of compounds was checked by m.p and TLC.

DMF (S.D. Fine's, A.R. grade) was dried in vacuum at 343 K. The densities of pure liquid and solutions have been measured by using a bicapillary pycnometer (made

of Borosil glass). The capillary, with graduated marks, had uniform bore and could be closed by a well-fitting glass cap. The marks on the capillary were calibrated by using triply distilled water. The speed of sound was measured by using Multifrequency Ultrasonic Interferometer (M-82, Mittal Enterprises, India) at 2 MHz. The uncertainty in measurements of ρ and u was within $\pm 2 \times 10^{-4}$ g cm⁻³, 0.05% respectively. The viscosity was measured by means of a suspended level Ubbelohde viscometer. The viscosity values were determined using the relation,

$$\eta = \rho (K_t - L/t) \quad (1)$$

where η is the viscosity, ρ is the density of the liquid, t is the flow time, K and L are characteristic constants for a given viscometer and were obtained by measuring the flow time of triply distilled water at temperatures (298.15, 303.15, 308.15 and 313.15 K) using the density and viscosity values of water from the literature. Linear regression analysis of a plot of η_t/ρ against t^2 for triply distilled water at five temperatures provides estimates of $K = 4.62 \times 10^{-9}$ m s⁻² and $L = -0.1656 \times 10^{-4}$ m² as slope and intercept of the plot, respectively with correlation coefficient 0.999. Estimated precision of experimental viscosities was 0.01 mPa.s.

The refractive indices were measured with a thermostated Abbe-refractometer after calibrating it with distilled water at known temperatures. The error in measurements of n_D was less than ± 0.001 units. The temperature of the solutions, during the measurements, was maintained to an accuracy of ± 0.1 K in an electronically controlled thermostated water bath (YSI-14).

The experimental values of density, viscosity, speed of sound and refractive index of pure DMF at 298.15 K [0.9947×10^3 kg m³, 0.796 mPa.s, 1456 m s⁻¹, 1.429] were found to be good agreement with corresponding literature values [0.9949×10^3 kg m³, 0.796 mPa.s, 1462 m s⁻¹ and 1.4282]^{8,9}.

Results and discussion

The experimental values of density (ρ), speed of sound (u), viscosity (η) and refractive index (n_D) of pure DMF and solutions of hydrazones in DMF as function of hydrazones concentration and temperature are reported in Table 1. The values of ρ and u have been used to calculate adiabatic compressibility (β_s), intermolecular free length (L_f), specific impedance (Z), relaxation strength

(r), relative association (R_A), internal pressure (P), solvation number (S_n) with help of following relations (2) to (8) and reported in Table 2.

$$\beta_s = 1/u^2\rho \quad (2)$$

$$L_f = K\beta_s^{1/2} \quad (3)$$

$$Z = u\rho \quad (4)$$

$$r = 1 - (u/u_\alpha) \quad (5)$$

$$R_A = (\rho/\rho_0)(u_0/u)^{1/3} \quad (6)$$

$$P_{\text{int}} = \alpha T/\beta_T \quad (7)$$

$$S_n = n_1/n_2 (1 - \beta_s/\beta_{s0}) \quad (8)$$

where ρ_0 and u_0 are density and speed of sound of pure DMF, K is Jacobson constant, M is molecular weight of hydrazone, α isothermal expansion coefficient, β_T isothermal compressibility¹⁰, n_1 , n_2 are no. of moles of solvent and no. of moles of solute. From Tables 1 and 2 it is evident that the values of density (ρ), speed of sound (u), viscosity (η), increases with increasing concentration of hydrazones at all studied temperatures.

Intermolecular free length is predominating factor in determining the variation of speed of sound in solution. In present investigation intermolecular free length at all studied temperatures, decreases with increase in concentration. It may be due to decrease in compressibility with increase in concentration which supports the significant interaction between solute and solvent molecule¹¹. It is obvious that increase in Z with increase in concentration is due to increase ρ and u with concentration. Decrease in Z value with rise of temperature again attribute to corresponding decrease in ρ and u with temperature. Adiabatic compressibility (β_s) and relaxation strength (r), decreases with concentration for both hydrazones in DMF. Decrease in β_s with concentration supported fully compressed solvated molecule by electrical forces present in solvent molecule due to strong solute and solvent interactions. As expected β_s and L_f are found to increase with temperature of the system. The value of R_A increases for both hydrazones with concentration and decreases with rise of temperature. Temperature increase result in an increase of intermolecular distance between surfaces of two molecules.

Internal pressure is cohesive force, which is a result of interaction between attractive and repulsive forces between the molecule of solution. Increase in value of inter-

Table 1. Densities (ρ), speed of sound (u), viscosity (η) and refractive indices (n_D) of HCAIH and HMAIH in DMF at temperatures 298.15, 303.15, 308.15 and 313.15 K

m (mol kg ⁻¹)	HCAIH + DMF				HMAIH + DMF			
	298.15 K	303.15 K	308.15 K	313.15 K	298.15 K	303.15 K	308.15 K	313.15 K
	$\rho \times 10^3$ (kg m ⁻³)							
0	0.9447	0.9397	0.9356	0.9298	0.9447	0.9397	0.9356	0.9298
0.0316	0.9470	0.9432	0.9392	0.9340	0.9487	0.9437	0.9397	0.9340
0.0633	0.9488	0.9456	0.9423	0.9378	0.9519	0.9470	0.9431	0.9376
0.0950	0.9494	0.9476	0.9443	0.9409	0.9544	0.9498	0.9458	0.9408
0.1267	0.9499	0.9491	0.9462	0.9438	0.9568	0.9521	0.9482	0.9435
0.1583	0.9502	0.9508	0.9481	0.9455	0.9585	0.9538	0.9499	0.9456
0.1900	0.9504	0.9526	0.9489	0.9476	0.9603	0.9556	0.9521	0.9474
0.2217	0.9508	0.9538	0.9508	0.9488	0.9616	0.9571	0.9539	0.9488
	u (m s ⁻¹)							
0	1456.0	1440.1	1420.2	1402.1	1456.0	1440.1	1420.2	1402.1
0.0316	1460.1	1443.2	1423.5	1405.2	1459.0	1444.3	1424.8	1408.2
0.0633	1463.4	1446.2	1426.3	1407.6	1462.2	1447.5	1429.2	1413.5
0.0950	1465.4	1447.8	1429.8	1410.2	1464.5	1450.2	1432.9	1417.3
0.1267	1467.3	1449.5	1432.2	1411.5	1466.8	1452.5	1435.5	1419.8
0.1583	1468.6	1450.2	1433.6	1414.1	1468.3	1454.6	1437.4	1422.2
0.1900	1469.2	1451.2	1434.8	1415.5	1469.7	1455.1	1439.2	1425.3
0.2217	1471.2	1452.8	1435.4	1417.1	1471.8	1457.2	1441.3	1428.6
	η (mPa.s)							
0	0.796	0.781	0.710	0.678				
0.0316	0.885	0.829	0.792	0.759	0.911	0.865	0.824	0.783
0.0633	0.901	0.855	0.812	0.777	0.916	0.876	0.838	0.798
0.0950	0.914	0.864	0.823	0.784	0.954	0.902	0.848	0.819
0.1267	0.924	0.876	0.837	0.793	0.961	0.920	0.869	0.831
0.1583	0.937	0.892	0.847	0.800	0.981	0.930	0.880	0.841
0.1900	0.958	0.904	0.855	0.814	1.001	0.959	0.901	0.856
0.2217	0.983	0.923	0.874	0.826	1.025	0.969	0.916	0.87
	n_D							
0	1.429	1.429	1.428	1.428	1.429	1.429	1.428	1.428
0.0316	1.446	1.443	1.442	1.441	1.448	1.445	1.444	1.442
0.0633	1.449	1.445	1.444	1.442	1.449	1.447	1.446	1.445
0.0950	1.449	1.446	1.445	1.443	1.451	1.451	1.447	1.446
0.1267	1.450	1.448	1.447	1.444	1.453	1.452	1.451	1.448
0.1583	1.451	1.450	1.448	1.445	1.454	1.453	1.452	1.451
0.1900	1.452	1.451	1.448	1.447	1.454	1.454	1.454	1.452
0.2217	1.453	1.453	1.449	1.449	1.455	1.455	1.455	1.454

Table 2. Adiabatic compressibility (β_s), intermolecular free length (L_f), specific impedance (Z), relaxation strength (r), internal pressure (P), solvation number (S_n), relative association (R_A) of HCAIH and HMAIH in DMF at temperatures 298.15, 303.15, 308.15 and 313.15 K

m (mol kg ⁻¹)	HCAIH + DMF				HMAIH + DMF			
	298.15 K	303.15 K	308.15 K	313.15 K	298.15 K	303.15 K	308.15 K	313.15 K
	$\beta_s \times 10^{-10}$ (m ³ N ⁻¹)							
0	4.993	5.131	5.299	5.471	4.993	5.131	5.299	5.471
0.0316	4.953	5.090	5.254	5.422	4.952	5.080	5.242	5.399
0.0633	4.921	5.056	5.216	5.382	4.914	5.039	5.191	5.338

Table-2 (contd.)

0.0950	4.904	5.035	5.180	5.344	4.885	5.006	5.150	5.292
0.1267	4.889	5.015	5.152	5.318	4.858	4.978	5.118	5.258
0.1583	4.879	5.001	5.130	5.289	4.839	4.955	5.095	5.228
0.1900	4.874	4.985	5.119	5.267	4.821	4.942	5.071	5.196
0.2217	4.859	4.967	5.104	5.248	4.801	4.920	5.047	5.164
$L_f \times 10^{-11}$ (m)								
0	4.458	4.520	4.630	4.749	4.458	4.520	4.630	4.749
0.0316	4.440	4.502	4.610	4.727	4.440	4.497	4.605	4.717
0.0633	4.426	4.487	4.594	4.710	4.423	4.480	4.582	4.691
0.0950	4.419	4.477	4.578	4.693	4.410	4.465	4.564	4.670
0.1267	4.412	4.468	4.565	4.682	4.398	4.452	4.550	4.655
0.1583	4.407	4.462	4.556	4.669	4.389	4.442	4.540	4.642
0.1900	4.405	4.455	4.551	4.659	4.381	4.436	4.529	4.628
0.2217	4.398	4.447	4.544	4.651	4.372	4.426	4.518	4.614
$Z \times 10^6$ (kg m ⁻² s ⁻¹)								
0	1.375	1.353	1.328	1.304	1.375	1.353	1.328	1.304
0.0316	1.382	1.361	1.337	1.313	1.384	1.363	1.339	1.315
0.0633	1.388	1.368	1.344	1.320	1.392	1.371	1.348	1.325
0.0950	1.391	1.372	1.350	1.327	1.398	1.377	1.356	1.333
0.1267	1.393	1.376	1.355	1.332	1.403	1.383	1.361	1.339
0.1583	1.395	1.379	1.359	1.338	1.407	1.387	1.365	1.345
0.1900	1.396	1.382	1.361	1.342	1.411	1.391	1.370	1.350
0.2217	1.399	1.386	1.364	1.345	1.415	1.395	1.375	1.355
r								
0	0.172	0.190	0.212	0.232	0.172	0.190	0.212	0.232
0.0316	0.167	0.186	0.208	0.228	0.168	0.185	0.207	0.225
0.0633	0.163	0.183	0.205	0.226	0.165	0.182	0.202	0.220
0.0950	0.161	0.181	0.201	0.223	0.162	0.179	0.198	0.215
0.1267	0.159	0.179	0.198	0.221	0.159	0.176	0.195	0.213
0.1583	0.157	0.178	0.197	0.219	0.158	0.174	0.193	0.209
0.1900	0.156	0.177	0.195	0.217	0.156	0.173	0.191	0.207
0.2217	0.154	0.176	0.195	0.216	0.154	0.171	0.189	0.203
$P \times 10^{-8}$ (Pa)								
0	4.535	4.535	4.521	4.502	4.535	4.535	4.521	4.502
0.0316	4.564	4.568	4.554	4.538	4.568	4.575	4.563	4.552
0.0633	4.586	4.594	4.582	4.568	4.599	4.607	4.600	4.595
0.0950	4.601	4.611	4.609	4.596	4.622	4.633	4.631	4.652
0.1267	4.612	4.627	4.630	4.616	4.644	4.656	4.656	4.656
0.1583	4.620	4.638	4.646	4.637	4.659	4.674	4.673	4.660
0.1900	4.625	4.652	4.656	4.654	4.675	4.686	4.693	4.666
0.2217	4.658	4.665	4.668	4.668	4.691	4.703	4.712	4.670
S_n								
0.0326	3.205	3.275	3.464	3.644	3.407	4.110	4.422	5.373
0.0633	2.814	2.990	3.191	3.330	3.268	3.650	4.178	4.965
0.0950	2.383	2.572	3.066	3.154	2.949	3.324	3.853	4.472
0.1267	2.100	2.322	2.834	2.855	2.775	3.049	3.499	3.983

Table-2 (contd.)

0.1583	1.848	2.079	2.583	2.720	2.525	2.810	3.151	3.627
0.1900	1.629	1.949	2.318	2.543	2.353	2.511	2.940	3.429
0.2217	1.581	1.867	2.146	2.377	2.254	2.402	2.788	3.276
R_A								
0.0316	1.0013	1.0030	1.0031	1.0039	1.0036	1.0033	1.0031	1.0034
0.0633	1.0022	1.0050	1.0058	1.0075	1.0063	1.0062	1.0061	1.0067
0.0950	1.0028	1.0067	1.0072	1.0103	1.0085	1.0086	1.0081	1.0089
0.1267	1.0029	1.0080	1.0088	1.0136	1.0105	1.0105	1.0101	1.0115
0.1583	1.0030	1.0096	1.0105	1.0144	1.0120	1.0119	1.0112	1.0129
0.1900	1.0034	1.0114	1.0111	1.0164	1.0136	1.0137	1.0139	1.0145
0.2217	1.0035	1.0123	1.0130	1.0173	1.0145	1.0149	1.0156	1.0148

nal pressure with increase in concentration confirms solute-solvent interaction.

The solvation number decreases with increase in concentration of hydrazones at all studied temperatures indicating increased solute-solute interaction with increasing concentration¹². Molecular interaction whatever that exists in solution is due to dipolar interactions between unlike molecule.

The apparent molar volumes (V_ϕ) and apparent molar adiabatic compressibility (K_ϕ) were calculated by the following equations :

$$V_\phi = M/\rho - \{10^3(\rho - \rho_0)/m \rho \rho_0\} \quad (9)$$

$$K_\phi = M \beta_s/\rho - \{10^3(\beta_{s0}\rho - \beta_s \rho_0)/m \rho \rho_0\} \quad (10)$$

where m is the molality of hydrazones in solution (unit : mol kg⁻¹), M is the molar mass of hydrazones, ρ_0 , ρ , β_{s0} and β_s are the densities (unit : kg m⁻³) and coefficient of adiabatic compressibilities of pure solvent and solution, respectively. The calculated values of apparent molar volumes (V_ϕ), adiabatic compressibilities (K_ϕ), as a function of concentration at different temperatures are given in Table 3.

Table 3. Apparent molar volume (V_ϕ) and apparent molar adiabatic compressibility (K_ϕ) of HCAIH and HMAIH in DMF at temperatures 298.15, 303.15, 308.15 and 313.15 K

m (mol kg ⁻¹)	HCAIH + DMF			
	298.15 K	303.15 K	308.18 K	313.15 K
	$V_\phi^0 \times 10^{-6}$ (m ³ mol ⁻¹)			
0.0316	224.57	182.20	178.82	157.14
0.0633	233.08	201.49	187.39	163.99
0.0950	249.99	212.35	203.15	174.35
0.1267	259.26	222.07	211.68	181.05

Table-3 (contd.)

0.1583	266.19	226.23	216.55	193.60
0.1900	271.42	228.29	226.47	199.40
0.2217	274.00	232.79	227.63	208.20
$K_\phi^0 \times 10^{-5}$ (m ³ mol ⁻¹ GPa ⁻¹)				
0.0316	-2.11	-5.70	-5.74	-6.43
0.0633	-0.43	-2.99	-4.17	-5.49
0.0950	2.48	-0.53	-2.88	-4.47
0.1267	4.07	1.05	-1.48	-2.94
0.1583	5.42	2.32	-0.17	-1.79
0.1900	6.64	2.97	1.46	-0.78
0.2217	6.94	3.53	2.24	0.36
HMAIH + DMF				
$V_\phi^0 \times 10^{-6}$ (m ³ mol ⁻¹)				
0.0316	142.40	142.40	138.78	135.05
0.0633	156.20	154.55	151.04	145.65
0.0950	168.70	164.19	163.17	153.65
0.1267	175.58	173.23	171.69	161.94
0.1583	184.46	182.74	181.67	171.04
0.1900	189.71	188.40	185.13	178.87
0.2217	195.92	193.88	189.60	186.46
$K_\phi^0 \times 10^{-5}$ (m ³ mol ⁻¹ GPa ⁻¹)				
0.0316	-6.67	-10.08	-12.05	-15.51
0.0633	-5.57	-7.59	-10.42	-13.97
0.0950	-3.73	-5.78	-8.44	-11.64
0.1267	-2.75	-4.22	-6.51	-9.17
0.1583	-1.34	-2.78	-4.52	-7.21
0.1900	-0.42	-1.27	-3.46	-6.01
0.2217	0.24	-0.58	-2.62	-5.02

Linear function of the molality over the studied range, the standard state (infinite dilution) partial molar volume, (V_ϕ^0) and partial molar adiabatic compressibility (K_ϕ^0) were obtained by least-square fitting to the equation :

$$Y_{\phi} = Y_{\phi}^0 + S_Q m_s \quad (11)$$

where Y_{ϕ}^0 (denotes V_{ϕ}^0 or K_{ϕ}^0) is the limiting value of apparent partial molar property (equal to the infinite dilution partial molar property) and S_Q (denotes S_v or S_k) is the experimental or limiting slope indicative of solute-solute interactions. The evaluated values of V_{ϕ}^0 , K_{ϕ}^0 and S_v , S_k are given in Table 4.

Table 4. Limiting partial molar properties $V_{\phi}^0 \times 10^{-6}$ ($\text{m}^3 \text{mol}^{-1}$) and $K_{\phi}^0 \times 10^{-5}$ ($\text{m}^3 \text{mol}^{-1} \text{GPa}^{-1}$) and experimental slope $S_v \times 10^{-6}$ ($\text{m}^3 \text{mol}^{-3/2} \text{L}^{1/2}$) and $S_k \times 10^{-5}$ ($\text{kg m}^3 \text{mol}^{-2} \text{GPa}^{-1}$) of HCAIH and HMAIH in DMF at temperatures 298.15, 303.15, 308.15 and 313.15 K

T (K)	HMAIH + DMF			
	V_{ϕ}^0	S_v	K_{ϕ}^0	S_k
298.15	219.60	272.10	-2.20	45.27
303.15	181.80	270.50	-5.98	50.23
308.15	173.40	268.32	-6.95	42.74
313.15	148.00	267.50	-7.69	35.93
HCAIH + DMF				
298.15	138.54	274.35	-7.66	37.65
303.15	136.98	271.36	-10.92	49.78
308.15	134.58	269.59	-13.45	52.02
313.15	127.82	268.39	-17.19	58.45

The volume behavior of solute satisfactorily represented by V_{ϕ}^0 , which provides information concerning solute-solvent interaction. Table 4 reveals that the values of V_{ϕ}^0 are large positive for both hydrazones, suggesting the presence of strong solute-solvent interaction in solution at all temperatures investigated^{13,15}. For hydrazones the values of V_{ϕ}^0 and S_v decreases with increase in temperature. This indicates molecular interaction becomes weaker with rise of temperature.

Negative values K_{ϕ}^0 are attributed due to the loss of structural compressibility of solvent molecule¹⁶. From the values of V_{ϕ}^0 and S_v , it is evident that molecular interaction is more in HCAIH than HMAIH in DMF, this may be due to the replacement of more electronegative chloro group in HCAIH by electron repelling methyl group in HMAIH.

The solute-solvent interaction can be discussed through the change of a dynamic property such as viscosity. The variation of relative viscosity for HCAIH and HMAIH in DMF can be represented by the Jones-Dole equation,

$$\eta_r = \eta/\eta_0 = 1 + AC^{1/2} + BC \quad (12)$$

where η_r is the relative viscosity; η and η_0 are the viscosities of solution and solvent; and C is the concentration, where A and B are the constants, characteristic of ion-ion and ion-solvent interaction, respectively. In the case of non-electrolytes, $A = 0$, and this reduces the Jones-Dole equation to

$$\eta_r = \eta/\eta_0 = 1 + BC \quad (13)$$

where B is the Jones-Dole B -coefficient and is obtained by plotting η_r against C , where slopes of the straight lines yield the B -coefficient. The B -coefficient measures size and shape effects as well as the structural effect induced by solute-solvent interaction¹⁷. A large and positive B -coefficient for HCAIH and HMAIH in DMF indicates a structure-making action (hydrophobic and hydrogen bonding actions) of solute on solvents¹⁸. The sign of dB/dT values gives important information regarding the structure-making and structure-breaking roles of solute in the solvent media. As evident from Table 5, a negative dB/dT trend was observed, which indications of the structure-making action of HCAIH and HMAIH due to hydrogen bonding¹⁹.

Table 5. Values of B ($10^{-6}/\text{m}^3 \text{mol}^{-1}$) coefficient of HCAIH and HMAIH in DMF at temperatures 298.15, 303.15, 308.15 and 313.15 K

T (K)	B	dB/dT	B	dB/dT
298.15	0.6126	0.7658	0.7658	
303.15	0.5849	0.7313	0.7313	
308.15	0.5660	0.6892	0.6892	
313.15	0.4818	-0.0082	0.6617	-0.0071

The experimental refractive index presented in Table 1 shows an increasing trend with increasing concentrations of hydrazones. Refractive index is directly related to the interactions in the solution. n_D data were used to calculate molar refractivity (R_D) using Lorentz-Lorenz equation :

$$R_D = [(n_D^2 - 1) - (n_D^2 + 2)] (X_1 M_1 + X_2 M_2/\rho) \quad (14)$$

where X_1 , X_2 and M_1 , M_2 are the mole fraction and molecular weight of the solute and solvent respectively. The variation of R_D at $T = 298.15$ K, as a function of hydrazone concentration, is depicted graphically in Fig. 1. Single temperature plots have been given as no significant variation was observed in R_D with temperature. The plots in Fig. 1 are found to increase linearly

Fig. 1. Variation of R_D vs m (moles/kg) for HCAIH and HMAIH in DMF at 298.15 K.

Table 6. Molar refractive index (R_D) of solutions and HCAIH HMAIH in DMF temperatures 298.15, 303.15, 308.15 and 313.15 K

m (mol kg ⁻¹)	$10^{-3} R_D$ (m ³ mol ⁻¹)			
	298.15 K	303.15 K	308.18 K	313.15 K
	HCAIH + DMF			
0	19.946	19.954	20.086	20.224
0.0316	20.732	20.696	20.739	20.813
0.0633	20.973	20.868	20.902	20.918
0.0950	21.098	21.012	21.044	21.038
0.1267	21.275	21.207	21.231	21.161
0.1583	21.456	21.397	21.375	21.309
0.1900	21.632	21.546	21.503	21.491
0.2217	21.808	21.744	21.646	21.692
	HMAIH + DMF			
0.0316	20.773	20.762	20.809	20.854
0.0633	20.891	20.918	20.964	21.046
0.0950	21.064	21.166	21.090	21.164
0.1267	21.239	21.303	21.350	21.333
0.1583	21.388	21.452	21.499	21.556
0.1900	21.493	21.599	21.679	21.703
0.2217	21.650	21.752	21.825	21.900

with increasing amount of solute. Since R_D is directly proportional to the molecular polarizability. Fig. 1 reveals that the overall polarizability of the system under study increases with increasing amount of hydrazones in the solution²⁰.

Conclusion :

In this investigation density (ρ), speed of sound (u),

viscosity (η) and refractive indices (n_D) of 2-hydroxy-5-chloroisonicotinoylhydrazone and 2-hydroxy-5-methylisonicotinoylhydrazone were measured in *N,N*-dimethylformamide at different temperatures and derived acoustical parameters suggested presence of strong molecular interactions among the mixing components. The value of V_ϕ^0 and S_v observed in both systems are positive and decreases with rise of temperature which suggesting the presence strong solute-solvent interactions in the systems which tends to become more weak as the temperature increases. V_ϕ^0 values are smaller than S_v values suggesting predominant solute-solute interaction in solutions at all temperatures investigated, this is also supported by decrease in value of S_n with increase in concentration of hydrazones. It is evident that from values of V_ϕ^0 and S_v molecular interactions are more in HCAIH than HMAIH in DMF. The negative value dB/dT suggests that hydrazones acts as structure maker in DMF through hydrogen bonding. The refractive index study shows that the polarisability of hydrazones in DMF increases as concentration of hydrazones increases.

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